

IN IBN SAUD'S PALACE

Glimpses of Life as Subject or Guest of an Arab Sultan

By AMEEN RIHANI

Along the palace wall at Riyadh, the capital of Abdul-Aziz ibn Saud, Sultan of Nejd [now King of Saudi Arabia] were clay benches in double tiers, filled with people, who had come out, I first thought, to see me, together with Seyyid Hashem, the Arab gentleman who was my *rafiq*, or companion, and our little caravan—Huwaidi, the cook, and the other servants. But I had forgotten that the Arabs are inquisitive. These people, about five hundred of them, mostly of the *Bedu*, sitting solemnly outside the palace and in the court and corridors within, were waiting, not meekly but like personages who had an appointment with their sovereign lord. Indeed, some of them had the mien of princes; others, whose rags were most conspicuous, dignified themselves with the inevitable bamboo stick, the curved end of which they held up to their lips, vacantly or pensively it matters not.

Thus they come to the palace twice a day for two square meals. Some of them carry, concealed under their *abas*, called *bushts* in Nejd, kettles or wooden platters for the purpose of taking some rice and lamb to their kith and kin in the black booths outside the city. These people have nothing to do in time of peace; they form a part of the Sultan's standing army, as it were, whom he has to feed and clothe and keep content. And many among them receive an allowance in money. Indeed, there are numerous pensioners in Riyadh, which is in a sense like Mecca, whose people live on the munificence of a religious tradition austere observed.

On certain days twice a year, winter and summer, there is a general distribution of clothes. And many of the beneficiaries, I was told, sell what they do not need. That is why there are so many hawkers and circulating auctioneers in Riyadh. And there are those who bring gifts to Riyadh and go back the richer for them—those who are not of the Sultan's subjects but come from distantly ancient places and tribes to make their *salaam*, folding slowly the miles, traveling by night and by day, impelled by a motive of admiration or of fear—a religious or a political motive—to pay their respects to the Long-of-Days.

Everything, in the smallest detail, goes through the Sultan's hands. The Master of Ceremonies makes a list every day of the visitors who arrive, a hundred or more, perhaps—name, tribe, town, the object of the visit are all set down—and presents it to the Sul-

tan, who goes over the list and marks near each name what the man is to receive in clothes, in provision and in money. The list then goes to Shalhoub for execution—Shalhoub the upright, Shalhoub the virtuous. Save the Sultan himself, he is, of a certainty, the busiest man in Riyadh, in all Nejd.

I visited him one day in his office, that is, among his stores, on the ground floor of the palace. He sat on a rug cross-legged, with bags of silver before him, two bookkeepers to his right, and to his left two clerks, one of whom had charge of the clothes, the other, of the money. Shalhoub counted out the *rupees* or the Maria Theresa dollars to those who came with orders, and then handed to them the clothes. "I do most of the work," said Shalhoub, in a plain, matter-of-fact manner. "A simple thing. A thousand comes in: we write it in the book. A thousand goes out: we write it in the book. And the result"—he stroked one palm against the other—"nothing."

Besides the stores on the ground floor of the palace are the refectories and a waiting-hall, where the native visitors are received before they are admitted to the *majlis* upstairs. The palace was not built on a preconceived plan; it grew in a free and spontaneous manner, which is characteristically Arabic. It took me many days to get my bearings in it, so tortuous are its halls and corridors and so ramified. There are at least ten big buildings, connected not by subterranean passages but, like the dwellings of many of the Sultan's subjects in Riyadh, by high-walled bridges.

One evening I said to the Sultan that I was puzzled by a certain question, which he only could clarify.

"Ask me everything," said His Highness.

I thanked him and said, "Do you deem it a religious duty to wage war against the *Mushrekin* [those who associate the saints with Allah in their prayers] for the purpose of making them unitarians?"

"No, no," he straightway declared, striking the carpet twice with his staff. And he continued: "Take Al-Hasa, for instance. We have there thirty thousands of the Shiahs, who live in peace and security. No one ever molests them. All we ask of them is not to be too demonstrative in public on their fête-days. Rest assured, *ya Ustaz*. We are not as some people imagine us."

But the good cheer and geniality of Ibn Saud have taught the natives of the capital nothing, have not affected in the least their saturnine and sanctimo-

nious spirit. Thou shalt not smoke. Thou shalt not sing. Thou shalt not wear silk robes. And, if one is found staying in his shop or dawdling in the street during the time of prayer, he is insulted by the zealous mosque-goer, or, at least, looked upon askance.

Yet I do not forget how nobly the Arabs respond to their Sultan's call and how fully they prove their valor. The order goes out of Riyadh, carried by *najjabs* to the farthest ends of the sultanate, that the rendezvous shall be at a certain well or in a certain vale on a certain day. And, on that day, at the appointed place gather many thousand men, of the cities, of the new towns, of the desert encampments, each riding his own *zelul*, armed with his own rifle, girded with his own ammunition, carrying his dates and a *qirbah* of water, ready to offer all he has for Allah and for Nejd. "In days of peace, we have to give them everything," said the Sultan, "but in the *jihad* they ask nothing of us." At all times they are happy in the enjoyment of the dominant virtue of his reign—justice.

The truth is that in Nejd as nowhere else in Arabia is the saying, "Justice is the foundation of the state," honored in theory and in practice. The justice of Ibn Saud! We hear the word on sea and on land as we travel to Nejd and through it.

One of the first manifestations of justice is security. I have traveled five months in the heart of Arabia. Although my bags, with locks broken, were with the baggage-train, which was often ahead of us, and although among my men were several of the Bedu, nothing, not even a sheet of paper, did I lose. But I offer not my own experience, which is exceptional. The Arabs themselves who travel in Nejd testify to the security that exists wherever Ibn Saud has sway.

What is the justice of Ibn Saud but the *shar*—the Koranic law—the justice of the Prophet? The difference between the *shar* in Nejd and in other Arab countries, however, is that in the former it is summarily enforced, without favor or discrimination. To the judge, as to the executioner, all the guilty heads and all the guilty hands are one. Many a right hand, in the early days of the Sultan's reign, was cut off for petty larceny: and many a head fell to the ground for an offense that, in other countries and under different circumstances, might have been extenuated, even pardoned.

Some men of the tribe of Benu Murrah, who came one day to the palace in Riyadh for food and clothes, departed, after receiving them, in the direction of Al-Hasa and, finding a drove of camels on the way, made off with them. The herdsman complained to the Sultan in Riyadh, who despatched a *najjab* to Ibn Jiluwi. The Amir, when the *najjab* arrived, sent out four hundred of his men, a hundred in each direction—north, east, south, west—to search for and capture the thieves. In less than twenty-four hours they captured also the stolen camels. When the Benu Murrah were brought before the Roman-Arab, there was a question, there was a reply and there was the word: "To the Square!" And, on the morning of that terrible day, the sword of the executioner flashed eight

times in the Square of Hofuf, and eight heads of the Benu Murrah danced on the ground.

"He who sees with the eye of his head only is a churl," said the Sultan; "but he who sees also with the eye of his heart is a man." Now, it has been my studied purpose to see with both eyes throughout my travels in Arabia; to see more, in truth, with "the eye of the heart," even though I had to penetrate through a hundred veils of tradition and custom. But when I came up against a stone wall of faith or stood before the transparencies of a mildewed human existence, I have often wished that I did not have an eye in my head.

I do not think it out of place to repeat here what I said to myself and set down in my diary on Christmas Day in Riyadh: "I have not the least doubt about it—a religion of love and mercy and tolerance is better than a religion imposed by the sword."

At the time I was a captive of malaria in the palace. For days the fever had whispered in my heart that word in which is the end of all things. And our brother the Sultan Abdul-Aziz ibn Saud, came to see us, carrying the latest medical invention, a thermometer, in one hand, and a bottle of lime-juice in the other. His face was sunshine in the room, and his words were a draft of clear spring water. "This will tell thee—hold it in thy hand—how many degrees thou hast above the health-heat," he said; "and this," holding up the bottle, "will soften and cool the inward of thee. Didst thou eat *kinkina*—quinine—today? Allah keep thee and ward the evil from thee! Eat of the *kinkina* three times a day." Allah keep thee, my dear Abdul-Aziz, my noble friend, my good doctor and nurse, I am eating nothing else.

The large room I lived in did not see a ray of sun the day long; the fever helped me to discover that it was also damp and that on the wall-side of the *masnads*, or cushions, was something like mildew. Moreover, the dust was everywhere—on and under the carpets, on the table, on my cot and clothes. And there would come Huwaidi, with his thumb stuck in a bowl of milk. As for Seyyid Hashem, who was responsible for my comfort, he would stand near the window with a mirror—my silver mirror, the only object of luxury that I carried with me—in his hand, fixing the *ighal* on his head and casually describing for my benefit the hardships of the road to Koweit. And always he would repeat, as one would hum a tune, "No water except in Al-Hafar."

"I may die, O Seyyid Hashem," said I, "before I get to Koweit."

"Philosophers are long-lived, ya Ustaz," replied the Seyyid imperturbably. "And suppose thou dost die on the way, thou wilt not grieve; thou hast seen Riyadh and the *Ikhwan*, and for that thou wilt be admitted into *Jannat*. What greater felicity couldst thou desire?"

The Sultan came to see me every day. One day he came in bringing with him a section of the map of Arabia, in English, to show me the distance between Hail and Riyadh; and it occurred to me, as I was examining the map, that I could render him a little

service by translating the names into Arabic. He was pleased with the idea but reluctant to accept my offer. He would not give his guest, his sick guest, such trouble. "But when I recover," I said, "I might not be inclined—I may not have the time." So he yielded.

There were three other sections as big as the one I had seen; and, when I put them all side by side, I saw what a task I had before me. Here was the biggest map—Scale—1:1,000,000—of Arabia extant. And it was, regarding the transliteration of Arabic nouns, full of inconsistencies. More annoying than the learned Arabist's caprice, however, was the delay of the servants in getting me the necessary material for the work. It took a day to get the red ink and a day to get the reed pen. The translation done, I had to have glue or mucilage or paste to make the map whole. So three servants were sent out, in different directions; and three days later a brown powder was brought, which was beaten in hot water into a paste. All's well. Fortunately I had a pair of scissors to trim the margins. But I had to have two sticks to roll upon them the two ends of the map, so it could be hung, as the Sultan desired. I could think of nothing better than palm ribs.

Huwaiti, who volunteered his service in this matter, disappeared for two days and on the third day showed up empty-handed. In my exasperation, I became feverish. He spoke in assuaging accents. "Allah protect thee and give thee health. I have hurried for thy sake. But we had to send out to the palm gardens, cut the branches and whittle them to make them even, as thou hast said; and now, since the nail must go into them and stay fast in them, we must keep them in the sun to dry."

I shall take a week's vacation, therefore—thanks to thee, O Huwaiti—while the palm rods are being seasoned. And then—I had almost forgotten the cord. But what matters another day's delay? After all, I think the job was well worth the gold watch that His Highness gave me after the map was hung.

In poetic haste, I allowed my fancy to dwell on a vacation of a week. But I had forgotten Seyyid Hashem and Huwaiti. They came to me pleading together for assistance. Seyyid Hashem related his plight. When in Basra, he had bought for the Sultan some flannels, which, being of a coarse material, had an unpleasant smell. To His Highness, who always, as I well knew, perfumed himself extravagantly, the smell, by contrast, was more offensive. He would not, therefore, wear the flannels until something had been done to deodorize them. And Seyyid Hashem, who was charged with the business, gave them to Huwaiti to wash. Huwaiti applied soap and water to them vigorously; but, after he had finished with them, he saw, with amazement and trepidation, that they had shrunk woefully. What is to be done? Stretch the flannels? He did so with all the strength of his shaggy arms, but they would not remain stretched.

Now Huwaiti, having been in cosmopolitan Basra, had seen or heard of the flat-iron. Fortunately, too, there was an iron at the palace. Forthwith he gets it and applies it. But it would not work in

Riyadh as it worked in Basra. Travel had apparently robbed it of its virtue. Now, the questions I had to solve were many indeed. Why will not the flat-iron work? Why will not the flannels remain stretched? What can be done to reinvest the one with its virtue, the other with its size? Can we, by bringing the iron to bear upon the flannel, make it stand out, in its deodorized state, as it did when it was tainted, a full-sized garment fit for a Sultan?

The flat-iron and the flannels were brought before the Inquisition. "Where is the fire?" Huwaiti did not think that the iron needed a fire. "Where is the water?" He did not think it needed water. "Where is the cloth?" He did not think it needed a cloth. Seyyid Hashem enveloped me with wondering, admiring eyes. The live coals were put into the iron; the cloth was spread on the table; the water in a bowl was at hand, and I was in an instant transformed from a Syrio-American Arab. Each garment was stretched on the table, and I spouted water at it like a whale. I applied my finger to my tongue and then to the sole of the flat-iron; and, finding the iron fit for action, with a neuritic arm forsooth I drove it so furiously that, two days later when the Sultan was wearing a suit of those flannels, the sleeves came down on the wrists far enough to spoil the esthetic value of the broad open sleeves of his robe.

Evidently, Seyyid Hashem, to save my own dignity, did not hesitate or blush to say that he had done the job himself; for the Sultan rewarded him with a silver watch.

"Is it the habit of the Sultan," I asked, "to give away watches—only watches—as rewards?"

"No, *billah!* he gives away clothes, food, money—you have seen with your eyes—even slaves and slave-girls. He has Christian girls, also. Ask him for one. *Wallah, ya Ustaz,* he will present one to you."

I had, in fact, heard of the Georgian women in Riyadh. And when I went to visit the Sultan's father, the Imam Abdur-Rahman, who is about eighty and dyes his beard with henna, I was told that he had in his harem two Gurjiyahs, or Georgian girls, and that one of them had recently given him a son. I do not know how many real Georgians, who are much prized in Nejd for their alabaster beauty, were among the poor Armenian girls that were bought in Syria in the year of the Red terror, when thousands of that race were expelled from their homes by the Turks and driven east and south into the wilderness. The traders of Nejd, who are always traveling between Kasim and Damascus, bought seventy or eighty Armenian girls that year and sold them as slaves. The Sultan purchased some of them, gave away a few to his relatives and friends and had two with him in Al-Hasa when we were there. They had been made to embrace Islam, these girls, and were taught the Koran.

One day His Highness took me up to the roof of the palace to show me the tower, from which the great incandescent lamp sends out at night penetrating white rays to the palm groves encircling Riyadh—a beacon to those who come from the desert or from the *wadi*. After escorting me to the tower, the Sultan

took me through another wing of the palace, to show me, on the parapeted roof of an adjacent building, the cannons and machine guns. These were about fifty in all, of English and German make, which he had won from the former King of Hejaz as well as from the Turks and Ibn Rashid.

His Highness would do well, I thought, if he cut short our tour of the palace by showing me a corner of the harem quarters. And he must have read my mind; for on the evening of that day, instead of calling on me as usual, he accorded me the privilege of sipping coffee with him in one of the very private apartments—after the Georgian girl had vacated it.

We had to go through a labyrinth to reach the apartment. A lamp hung in the vestibule, which led to a cozy little room, furnished in the usual way with carpets and *masnads*. It had no windows, not even, apparently, an aperture. But the Sultan, who does not disdain to show the hidden virtues of his living-rooms, got up and pulled a cord, which opened a square aperture in the wall near the ceiling. "For the sun and air," he said. He then pointed to a sword that was hanging on a peg. "It is the most cherished of all my possessions." He ordered a slave to bring it down. The hilt is of chased gold, the scabbard, of silver. Since it is the sword of the great Saud, his ancestor, it must be more than a hundred years old. The blade looks even older. The Sultan took it in his hand and told us how he had killed with it one of his bitterest foes. It was in revenge—a lawful and honored custom. "It was a joyous moment—I kissed the sword."

He then brought out a leather case of perfumes and insisted on perfuming me from the various bottles: one scent on my beard, another on my *gutrah*, a third on my breast—and they were all as heavy as undiluted attar of roses. As for Seyyid Hashem, he helped himself to them all recklessly. The room itself reeked. My head began to swim. I was ready to faint. The Sultan laughingly chided Seyyid Hashem. "A *seyyid* never knows his limits," he said, and forthwith offered me a fan.

On the following day we got a better view of what was beyond the iron gate through which, the night before, the Sultan had disappeared across the bridge after showing us through the Gurjyah's quarters; for, still with His Highness as guide, we crossed three roofs, two bridges and several corridors to his own private apartment, from which we beheld a row of four or five massive buildings columned and crenelated. "That is the harem," he said; "each one has a house of her own." In the vestibule—a sort of antechamber—where we had coffee, are two doors, one leading to the private *masjid* where the Sultan prays—he goes to the Grand Mosque on Friday only—the other leading to the apartment, which no woman ever enters.

Before leaving us that day, he showed me the place, a gallery of one of the quadrangles below, from which I might take a picture of the wedding-feast. For there had been a wedding in the palace the day or the night before. The bridegroom was a young

Saud—a boy of thirteen in fact. "He wanted to get married," said the Sultan nonchalantly, "and we got him married." His wife was his cousin, who was a girl of twelve.

It was the Sultan, in this instance, who had to give the wedding-feast; for the relatives of the married couple, as well as their parents, slay sheep and camels for those who may come. Every one is welcome. More than three thousand persons gorged themselves, at four or five sittings, with rice and lamb. Shalhoub supplied the exact figures. "Wallah!" he swore, "they gave me but one day to prepare; and you saw the result. Oh, yes; we have vessels that hold a whole camel. We slaughtered eighty sheep and thirty camels. And we emptied twenty bags of the best rice."

Besides the refectories, three open courts in the palace were filled. People of all classes sat in rows facing one another, and a sort of table-and-tray combined, made of metal, was placed over a round mat between each two groups of ten or fifteen. As soon as this was done, the lines formed into circles. The large trays of rice and lamb were then brought in, and every one tucked his sleeves and waited for the Sultan, who sat among one of the groups, to begin. He had to give a sign. He spoke. He uttered a prayer. And it was the shortest and the most effective prayer I have ever heard. "Think of Allah," said he in a loud voice, "and Allah will think of you." The hands of the guests were held still for a moment over the bounty of the day, and then they fell to.

Seyyid Hashem and I were watching from the gallery above; and I tried, by setting the camera in one of the loopholes of the crenelated parapet, to take a picture. Light there was still; but also there were many watchful eyes among the Ikhwan, who resented being photographed. Hence, through alternate hesitation and haste, failure in the attempt. But the joy of the adventure was at the end of the feast, when the Sultan came up and surprised us on the stairs, laughing like a boy who had taken part in a conspiracy against the schoolmaster.

Wisely spoke Shalhoub, the virtuous and strenuous Shalhoub. "Thou hast seen with thy two eyes. Now write down in thy book—for what I tell thee is truth—write, Allah keep thee: 'Every king in the world is supported by his people; but the people of Nejd are supported by their king.'"

Having endeavored to give a faithful picture of Riyadh, I must not omit what in itself is the most telling passage, a word said to me one evening by the Sultan Abdul-Aziz ibn Saud himself. He feels that he is a stranger in his own capital. People come to his majlis every day without leaving an impression to cherish. Between them and him there is no contact of mind or heart or even of soul. And the chasm ever yawns. He would not live in Riyadh a single day were he not the ruler of the country. He is, in truth, far above the ablest and the best—a palm-tree in a field of stubble, a lone pine in a wadi of brambles and thorns.